

Quantum Interference and Non-interference Based Entropies

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Quantum mechanics is based on two different probability schemes, namely $W(x)$ = wavefunction and $W^*(x)W(x) = P(x)$, with one being linked to the other. Why should there be two probability schemes? In (0) we argued that there are two spatial behaviour schemes because an impulse p (momentum) is automatically associated with two spatial distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ in $\exp(ipx)$, yet a particle with constant p moves as $x = p/m t$. Thus if one is only concerned with motion, each x point has the same weight, and this is physically measurable as a photon or electron travels a certain distance in a certain time in free space. On the other hand, an impulse interaction is associated with $\exp(ipx)$ is a completely different spatial picture, and this too is measurable as in a 2-slit experiment. Thus it seems the two schemes are measured differently.

We argue that this is an important issue because if there are two x -probability schemes there should be different entropies associated with each. Traditionally (1), one sees two quantum entropies: $-W^*(x)W(x) \ln \{W^*(x)W(x)\}$ and $-a^*(p)a(p) \ln \{a^*(p)a(p)\}$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. These are associated with the $x = p/m t$ scheme or x -dependence based on motion or average motion. $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents spatial density which should be measured presumably by some sort of scattering, but we ask whether some information is lost in this approach? In particular, we note that a wavefunction may be obtained for a bound state. In the high energy limit, the envelope over the density $W^*(x)W(x)$ is said (2) to match $C/v(x)$ from classical physics where $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. $C/v(x)$, however, is proportional to Δt (with Δx being constant) and has nothing to do with the strength of an impulse hit. In the classical case, there is a single $v(x)$ and so a single $p(x)$ in each Δx thus no impulse entropy within a Δx i.e. at a point x . In quantum mechanics, however, we argue that a constant p automatically has an x probability distribution $\exp(ipx)$ associated with it and there might be an entropy linked to this. This entropy is associated with a probability to receive a p impulse at x and is so not linked to interference while the $W^*(x)W(x)$ is.

In (3) we introduced the impulse or wavelength entropy (for a free particle $|\cos(px)|/C \ln\{|\cos(px)|/C\}$), but here we wish to investigate its properties more closely.

Quantum Mechanics and the Wavefunction

The quantum wavefunction is often introduced as a mathematical function $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ such that:

$$W^*(x)W(x) = P(x) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad a^*(p)a(p) = P(p) \quad ((1b))$$

Unlike classical statistical mechanics, if one knows about $P(x)$, one knows nothing about momentum at x and vice versa. Thus one may form the Shannon's entropies (1):

$$-W^*(x)W(x) \ln \{W^*(x)W(x)\} \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad -a^*(p)a(p) \ln \{a^*(p)a(p)\} \quad ((2b))$$

The issue we have with ((2)) is that quantum mechanical probability operates at two levels, both of which are physical.

If one considers a free particle with $W(x)=\exp(ipx) C$ then, $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ and $x=p/m t$, but there are two physically relevant x-probabilities associated with the impulse i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ which are visible in a 2-slit experiment etc. Thus there are two probability schemes. A photon or quantum particle moving towards a slit follows $x=p/m t$ which is connected with a probability scheme, related to motion. A completely different probability scheme $\exp(ipix)$, however, is associated with an impulse interaction at the two slits. If there are two different probability schemes there should be two different entropy schemes, we argue.

These two entropies, however, need to be understood.

Classical Bound State

A classical bound state is described by: $p(x)p(px)/2m + V(x) = E$ ((3))

In (2) the spatial density of such a system with the x axis broken into equal dx's each with a different dt(x) is given by:

$$P(x) dx = C1 \delta(t) = C2 dx/v(x) \quad ((4))$$

Thus there is a spatial density due to the speed of the particle, not due to impulses. A very fast particle has a tiny density because $\delta(t)$ is tiny. If a collision with a measuring particle does, however, occur, the impulse is very high, but this information is completely lost in the statement $P(x)=C2/v(x)$. A low $P(x)$ implies that a particle does not spend much time in dx, but gives no sense of "pressure" within dx. There is no p distribution with dx because classically one has a single $p(x)$ at each x.

A quantum bound state is described by the density $W^*(x)W(x)$, but what is the physical meaning of this? In a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, density(x) is linked to pressure via the ideal gas law:

$$\text{Pressure} = \text{density} R \text{ Temperature} \quad ((5))$$

Thus physical density and pressure are directly linked unlike the classical case of $P(x) = C2/v(x)$.

$W^*(x)W(x)$ is associated with $P(x)=C2/v(x)$ (see (2)) because in the high energy level limit, the envelope of $W^*(x)W(x)$ is the same as $C2/v(x)$. In fact, the quantum entropy ((2a)) in the high energy limit is evaluated by (2) using the classical result $C2/v(x)$ which does not account for impulse. We point out, however, that ((2a)) is based on interference of different magnitude p values.

Impulse Momentum

((5)) indicates that in a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas pressure is proportional to density which is a physical property. The relationship between "pressure"/impulse and spatial density is not accounted for in $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ or $P(x)=C2/v(x)$ we argue.

An MB gas has a pressure which acts like a scalar in the sense that one multiplies impulse $2p$ (a vector with 2 directions) with flux v (which also has two directions). Thus $p v = -p(-v)$.

We note that in an MB gas, the distribution (for no $V(x)$ is $\exp(-pp/2mT)$). The exponential form is also found in a quantum free particle $\exp(ipx)$, but here p is a vector taking on two values ($-p$ and p in one dimension). Furthermore, there is no velocity within a wavelength and hence no sense of pressure, but there is an impulse p . For a quantum bound state one has: $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

One may ask: What is the probability to have an impulse $|p|$ at x ? We use $|p|$ in order to try to mimic the notion of pressure which is the same in both directions if $a(p)=a(-p)$. This probability is not due to the interference of different p magnitude values. Thus the probability for a free particle in this picture is:

$$P(p,x) = |\cos(px)|/C \text{ over half a wavelength } ((6))$$

In order to motivate ((6)) we consider the following type of measurement. We wish to find a distribution of impulse hits (not spatial density hits). In such a case, even though $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ shows interference of different p 's, we consider that an impulse hit occurs off of one p or another and this information is retained. This is why $||$ is used with $\cos(px)$ and p and x appear in $P(p,x)$. Thus we would define an impulse entropy density at x as:

$$S(x) = - \text{Sum over } p |a(p)\cos(px)|/C \ln\{ |a(p)\cos(px)|/C \} \quad ((7)) \text{ where } C \text{ is a normalization constant}$$

The x range is over a length roughly equal to the classical turning points in the quantum bound state.

The impulse entropy ((7)) is a measure of the uncertainty of impulse hits at x . This is not the same as the uncertainty of getting any kind of hit at x represented by $W^*(x)W(x)$ due to average speeds. In other words, ((7)) is a Maxwell-Boltzmann type entropy linked to impulse (or the similar idea of pressure) and not to the amount of time a particle spends within a dx region (due to average speed).

Quantum Mechanics and Two Sets of Probabilities

We have argued above for two sets of entropies, the $W^*(x)W(x) / a^*(p)a(p)$ entropies versus the $a(p)\exp(ipx) \rightarrow a(p) | \cos(px)|/C$ entropy due to the presence of two very different probability schemes.

For a free particle, these are: $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ and $1/L$. The first is linked with periodic probability humps in space, the other with uniform probability in x . Thus there is a big difference, even though the two are linked. Simplifying considering $x=vt$ does not lead to the notion of interference patterns for example.

We argue that the quantum wavefunction $W(x)$ is not simply a square root probability mathematical quantity, but represents non-motion x dependent probability based on the impulses $\exp(ipx)$. Thus there is motion x dependence and momentum/impulse based x dependence. The latter creates the sense of the former, but two mathematical expressions for entropy also follow.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics is linked to two kinds of x dependence. First there is the classical x -dependence through motion (not interaction). For example, a particle with constant momentum moves as $x=p/m t$ (nonrelativistically) in a region with no potential. As a result, this is linked with a certain kind of entropy. The quantum spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ for high energies has an envelope linked to the classical bound density $P(x)= C_1 \delta(t) = C_2/v(x)$, but this is simply associated with the time the particle spends in dx . It is not linked with the notion of pressure that one sees in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas i.e. $\text{Pressure} = \text{density}(x)RT$. Thus we argue that there is a second entropy in quantum mechanics (outlined in (3)) which is linked to impulses and the distributions of $\exp(ipx)$ associated with each p . Given that there is no sense of velocity within a wavelength and hence no pressure, we consider a similar scalar function $a(p)\{\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)\}$ with $a(p)=a(-p)$. We then create an impulse entropy using Shannon's entropy and the probability $P(p,x) = |a(p)\cos(px)/C|$ as in (3).

References

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